

Asian Journal of Religious Studies

“The Lord is truly among us.”

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Encouraging and Supporting Brother Priests

Pope Francis' letter on the 160th anniversary of the death of the Curé of Ars, St John Vianney: support, closeness and encouragement to all priests who, despite their hard work and disappointments, celebrate the sacraments every day and accompany the people of God. Through his letter, he expresses his thanks for the daily service of so many priests who accompany the people of God in every part of the world

The scandal of abuse, the cry of dismay from the victims who have suffered unimaginably weighs down like a burden on the shoulders of every priest. There are priests who are looked upon with indignation, suspicion, through no fault of their own, but who remain bleeding wounds for the entire ecclesial body, recalls the Pope.

Pope Francis calls Curé of Ars, a model priest who served the people of God. The letter is broadly divided into four parts: Pain, Gratitude, Encouragement and Praise.

The Pope, who certainly did not falter in the face of the duty to denounce and reprimand when necessary, responds by thanking the silent army of priests who betrayed neither faith nor trust. He showed his closeness, encouragement, support and comfort to all priests in the world. To those priests who every day, often with difficulty, defying disappointment and incomprehension,

keep the churches open and celebrate the sacraments. To those priests who, overcoming sadness and habituality, continue to put themselves at risk in welcoming those who need a word, comfort and accompaniment. To those priests who daily visit their people, giving themselves up unreservedly, crying with those in tears and rejoicing with those in joy. To those priests who live "in the trenches", who sometimes risk their lives to be close to their people. To those priests who have to go through days and days of canoeing to reach some remote village to go and visit the isolated sheep of their flock, reports Vatican News.

There is a greatness not often recounted in the ordinary life of the Church. A greatness capable of making history even if it will never conquer the pages of guidebooks or the lights of the limelight. It is the greatness of service in hiding, of those who give themselves without being protagonists, trusting only in the grace of God. It is the greatness of a life given to others by those priests "forgiven sinners", as the Pope also defines himself, who have experienced and continue to experience mercy, who leave the initiative to God and follow him in the service of their communities.

There was a need for a word of encouragement, esteem, closeness. There was a need for thanksgiving like that contained in the pages of the papal letter. So that the pain caused to the ecclesial body by the infidelities of a few - as happened with the tremendous plague of abuse - would not risk forgetting the fidelity of many, experienced priests, despite the many labours and human limitations, reports Vatican News.

For this reason, Pope Francis wanted to give thanks to those who still today offer their entire existence to God by serving him in his people, and renews that initial "yes" of their vocation by remembering the call received.

The next issue will discuss this special letter written by a brother-priest to all priests!

-The Editor

How Can We Understand Yoga and its Practice as a Christian Believer?

+ *Thomas Mar Koorilos*

Metropolitan Archbishop of Tiruvalla

To begin let me quote NA 2 of Vatican II where it says: “The Catholic rejects nothing of what is true and holy in these religions. She has a high regard for the manner of life and conduct, the precepts and doctrines which, although differing in many ways from her own teaching, nevertheless often reflect a ray of that truth which enlightens all men. The Church, therefore, urges her sons to enter with prudence and charity into discussion and collaboration with members of other religions. Let Christians, while witnessing to their own faith and way of life, acknowledge, preserve and encourage the spiritual and moral truths found among non-Christians, also their social life and culture.”

This is the general attitude and conviction of the Catholic Church regarding other religions and their beliefs and practices. Though the history of yoga traces its beyond the Arian religion, namely Hinduism, Buddhism and Jainism (refer the researches done around 1920 in Harappa- Mohanjedaro: KCBC Kraisthava Vishwasavum Yogacharyum - Christian Faith and practice of yoga, POC Kochi 2019), yoga is now more identified with organized religion. So people identify easily yoga with Hinduism or Buddhism. Of course, yoga has been developed systematically by the Hindu Sanyasis. The contribution of Pathanjali Maharshi (around 5th Cent. BC) is commendable in this regard and he has

made it a discipline beyond that of religion and mainly as a psycho-spiritual art and has kept God outside of yoga's purview.

We know that the Christian mystics and desert fathers have made use of meditation and silence as ways to deepen spiritual experience of God. Following this wisdom of the fathers, many in India have tried yoga for deepening spiritual quest and union with the divine. Some examples are Robert De Nobili, Francis Acharya, Bede Griffiths, Sara Grant, etc. Following the teachings of the Vat. II on other religions, esp., the quote above, many have felt that yoga would be a good sign of inculturation and could bring the followers of other religion, especially Hindus into a dialogue of life. They felt that yoga is more of an art to discipline the body and mind which would help the person to be more disposed to the promptings of the divine.

“Some physical exercises automatically produce a feeling of quiet and relaxation, pleasing sensations, perhaps even phenomena of light and of warmth, which resemble spiritual well-being. To take such feelings for the authentic consolations of the Holy Spirit would be a totally erroneous way of conceiving the spiritual life. That does not mean that genuine practices of meditation which come from the Christian East and from the great non-Christian religions, which prove attractive to the man of today who is divided and disoriented, cannot constitute a suitable means of helping the person who prays to come before God with an interior peace, even in the midst of external pressures.”(Some Aspects of Christian Meditation, Cong. For Doctrine of Faith, Oct. 15, 1989, No. 28).

Having said these I am given to understand that there are a few discussions on whether a Christian can practice yoga. Is it something against faith or while practicing yoga what should a Christian be aware of? In 2015 UN has declared June 21 as International Yoga day. Ever since that time, yoga which was believed to be solely Indian got a universal recognition and in the present day life situations more and more people begin to practice yoga in their own way with their own understanding. We must say that

some reject outright yoga and any type of inculturation as against Christian faith and consider them as sinful. Some feel that there is absolutely no problem in practicing yoga and the various types of meditations because they all lead to serenity and spiritual depth and enlightenment. They are too optimistic. A good number of people take yoga as a tool or as an exercise pattern for body and mind without going into the philosophical and spiritual intricacies. There are also some who feel that like music or art one can also Christianize yoga and use it. The Kerala Catholic Bishops' Council has studied this matter and come out with solid teaching treating yoga in its entirety. It may be good to refer to this matter for those who would like to have a detailed view. I feel also that we should not exaggerate something which is not central to our life and faith. In our dealings and treatment, the unimportant should not become important and vice versa.

The Second Vatican Council has taught us that there are elements of truth and goodness in other religions and whatever good lies latent in the religious practices and cultures of diverse peoples, is not only saved from destruction but is also cleansed, raised and perfected unto the glory of God (LG 17). But whatever truth and grace are to be found among the nations, as a sort of secret presence of God, He frees from all taint of evil and restores to Christ its maker, who overthrows the devil's domain and wards off the manifold malice of vice. And so, whatever good is found to be sown in the hearts and minds of men, or in the rites and cultures peculiar to various peoples, not only is not lost, but is healed, uplifted, and perfected for the glory of God, the shame of the demon, and the bliss of men (AG 9).

Living in India, it is the duty of us to find ways and means to help the gospel values sink deep into the culture and milieu of our land. We need to deepen our Christian faith and practices through the various elements found in this culture,(of course that are not against the mind of Christ) because that is the way our people understand the gospel and Jesus Christ, the Word made God. It is better to recall the statement of Mahatma Gandhi who said, un-

less for the Christians, he would have been a follower of Christ. Knowingly or unknowingly or better to say unwittingly, we made Christianity look foreign, and the elements in this land pagan and unacceptable. Let us put into practice the call of the Second Vatican Council to dialogue with the world, dialogue with cultures and dialogue with religions. We must know that yoga has now become an item in school curriculum and our young generation is learning this. We cannot shut our eyes to these realities. Hence we have to evaluate where practice of yoga may become unacceptable to Christian faith or rather we need to caution our people the possible dangers while doing yoga.

As we have seen some people make use of yoga for preparing the body and mind for meditation and contemplation; some use yoga for deep mystical experience and some others take yoga like the Buddhist to empty the mind and body from God experience or rather reducing God to some earthly reality. The Church is against the last type of yoga practice which aims at limiting meditation for emptying or for self fulfillment without any reference to the Almighty God revealed through the incarnate Word, Jesus Christ. The person praying creating an empty space so that it may fill by the richness of God is welcome. The emptiness which God requires is that of the renunciation of personal selfishness, not necessarily that of the renunciation of those created things which he has given us and among which he has placed us. There is no doubt that in prayer one should concentrate entirely on God and as far as possible exclude the things of this world which bind us to our selfishness. On this topic St. Augustine is an excellent teacher: if you want to find God, he says, abandon the exterior world and re-enter into yourself. However, he continues, do not remain in yourself, but go beyond yourself because you are not God: He is deeper and greater than you. "I look for his substance in my soul and I do not find it; I have however meditated on the search for God and, reaching out to him, through created things, I have sought to know 'the invisible perfections of God' (Rom 1:20)." "To remain in oneself": this is the real danger. The great Doctor of the Church recommends, concentrating on oneself, but

also transcending the self which is not God, but only a creature. God is "deeper than my inmost being and higher than my greatest height." In fact God is in us and with us, but he transcends us in his mystery (Some Aspects of Christian Meditation..., Nr. 19).

Of late some tendencies connected with the New Age have become very noticeable. This is in the understanding of spirituality and God experience. Spirituality is more connected to ones' serenity, feeling good, unrelated to people and things, being good to oneself and so on. One feels that one can be a spiritual person without being related to God or connected to the Divine. What matters is one's equanimity, serenity, enlightenment, and so on. In this area yoga and transcendental meditation and tantric exercises can become dangerous for faith life. This is the caution that the recent Church teachings on yoga puts forth to its members. Yet another danger is the possibility of considering grace and peace as something created and earned through one's efforts, without considering them as the Gifts of the Holy Spirit. These are very narrow and subtle differences but very significant ones which may easily lead people to syncretic spirituality. Again it must be borne in mind that in yoga one finds one's salvation in self-fulfillment and realizing the God element in oneself. But we know that in the Christian faith salvation is communion with the triune God and in relationship with others. So also prayer or meditation in yoga is more of conversing with oneself and for a Christian it is communicating with God and learning to be obedient to his will. What is therefore needed is training our faithful well to use yoga to prepare the mind and body for deeper God experience in prayer. People must be helped to distinguish between supernatural grace and feeling good experience in yoga or meditation. The Holy Father Pope Francis in his address has eloquently said: "You can follow a thousand catechism courses, a thousand yoga or Zen courses and all these things. But none of this will be able to give you the freedom as a child of God" (Vatican Radio Address, Jan 9, 2016). He has also cautioned that yoga can lead one to erroneous faith and syncretic spirituality. But the Pope has never denied its good effects on mind and body.

Yoga can be helpful in this modern age where people are overloaded with stress and tensions. People get easily upset and feel worn out. Here practice of yoga can help people to get refreshed in mind and body. The syncronization of the body and mind is very essential. In Pranayama a Christian can breathe in remembering the Triune God. I know some people doing Soorya Namaskaram reciting the Lord's Prayer for each step.

Thus I find it is a responsibility of the Christians to Christianize yoga. It will be a great help to keep our body and mind agile, healthy and sensitive to the world outside. Moreover, a serene mind, a disposed body and inner tranquility will definitely help a person to deepen his relationship to God, the core of one's being and to his fellow human beings. Today's big problem is that man is not at home with himself. He is torn apart and divided within himself. His tranquility and equanimity are lost. Yoga will definitely help in this stage. It will also help us to be devoid of our passions and compulsory fixations. They say yoga is the golden key that unlocks the door to peace, tranquility and joy. Yoga is not a must for a Christian to deepen his spiritual journey; but it is helpful to present ourselves to be physically and mentally prepared to receive Christ the Word. It is like the soil being prepared well to receive the seeds to produce 100 fold fruits. But if only the soil is prepared and no seed is sown, then it is useless.

Culture, Religion and Food Security for Indian Women: A Social Perspective

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Food security is a state of having a source of access to enough quantity of affordable and nutritious food. Food and food related practices stem from the social construction of gendered roles and responsibilities that assigns the liability of feeding the family to a feminine quality and responsibility. The gendered stereotype of women as primary nurturers, caregivers for children and family members is a notion deeply entrenched in the patriarchal ideologies of society. India being one such society, the onus of ‘providing’ for the family’s food needs is viewed as a woman’s liability. Family food security exists when all its members, always, have access to enough food for an active, healthy life. Social institutions such as ‘family’ and ‘religion’ have been the drivers for determining food related practices and food security in the family.

The ideologies of gender stratification, gender roles and religious ideologies has further created a sense of greater liability ingrained in the psyche of almost every Indian woman. This in turn leads the woman to feel and think that she is respon-

sible for the food needs and wellbeing of her family. This is largely constructed around women's identity, leaving women, in many instances solely responsible for food needs of the family. Providing for the family's food needs has remained in the imagination of society as the sole responsibility of women and is therefore closely connected to the everyday lives of women. As wives and mothers, women are assigned with the duty of feeding the family and are viewed as exclusively responsible in defeating hunger in the family. In doing so they become victims of hunger themselves. The fact that women are held responsible for nutritional requirements that must fulfill the needs of their families is a burden that has fallen upon the shoulders of women. This therefore is a serious anomaly that needs to be corrected by concerned social workers, development practitioners and by women themselves. Important documents among many others, such as India's Food Security Act of 2013 and the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women of 2014 (CEDAW) ensures 'equal right to food' for women, however little progress has been made in this effort.

Food and Indian Women

This article stems from field observations of a survey on 'Women and Food Security', carried out in the lesser developed urban areas of Chennai city. The Coping Strategies Index (CSI) a tool based on collecting data on a single question: 'What do you do when you do not have enough food, and do not have money to buy food?' (Maxwell, Daniel G 1996) was used. The use of other participatory techniques such as focus group discussion (FGDs) and observations were used to gather information. The method goes beyond measuring merely caloric consumption but specifically observes the vulnerability elements such as access to food, cultural and religious practices and gendered

patterns of food consumption. The study gained deep insights into the daily lives of the lesser privileged women. It further found that food insecurity among the women in the city points to a challenge that leads to higher levels of vulnerability of the family in terms of a poor quality of life. This study therefore suggests some strategic interventions that can mitigate the vulnerability element of food insecurity among women.

Culture and religion to a large extent shape a family's diet, food needs, food distribution patterns, child feeding practices and even food preparation techniques. In a patriarchal society such as India, a food related belief is that the woman eats last or the leftovers after the man and sons of the house have eaten. Beliefs such as regular fasting for the wellbeing of the family on the woman is yet another practice that deters women's psychological and physical wellbeing. Such practices tend to make the woman believe that she is virtuous, moral and worthy. These are deep-rooted and internalized socio-cultural and religious beliefs that cannot be erased easily. Several such practices have had a negative impact on the health and wellbeing of women. Challenging such beliefs is a task at hand to be tactfully addressed by those concerned in upholding gender justice, faith formation and value-based education.

Studies on maternal health and child health provide a glimpse of the status of food and nutrition security of women, but finds that there is an absolute dearth of social security cover of any sort for younger widows, homeless women, women whose husbands have been reportedly missing or labelled as terrorist, unwed mothers, abandoned women, separated or divorced women, never-married women, disabled and mentally ill women who are undoubtedly the most vulnerable in terms of food and nutrition (Mander, 2016; Dand, 2016).

It is a well-known fact that poor women all over the world, are left hungry most of the times. The fact that women are responsible for food provision that must fulfill the needs of children and family members, falls as a greater burden on the shoulders of women in the family. It is therefore important to look at food and femininity from a socio-cultural, religious and gendered reality. Women who are in poverty situations, are denied access to important resources such as credit, land and inheritance. Their hard work in the form of farm and home labour goes unrewarded and unrecognized. Their health and nutritional needs are not crucial for development, they are deprived of to education and support services, and their participation in decision-making at home and in the community are not included or otherwise is minimal. Caught in the cycle they are not able change the deplorable situation that they find themselves in. (Kariuki J. G. 2013).

India has nearly forty percent of the world's under-nourished population (FAO, 2012). With one-third of its children malnourished, one-third of its women undernourished, half of its women anaemic, India growth trajectory cannot be termed 'impressive'. In many other social indices particularly related to women's nutritional status, like low birthweight of infants, maternal mortality and morbidity, India has performed poorly. As per Sample Registration System (SRS) data from 2011- 2013, India has a Maternal Mortality Rate (MMR) of 167 per 100,000 births compared to 14 in developed states (Press Information Bureau, 2015). MMR is an important indicator of women's health and nutrition status and has been a priority area for the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Reproductive health and women's food and nutritional security have been low priority areas in India, in terms of public spending as well as social perception.

The lack of recognition of women's indirect contribution to the growth of an economy by way of their reproductive and home-care roles as workers can be attributed as one of the main causes in leaving women and their families poorer and hungrier. The work at home of raising children, care of the sick and elderly, cattle grazing, fetching fuel, fodder and water have all been the main contention in recognizing women's work. Food security particularly for women is a recent addition to the dimension of right to food. An aspect that needs recognition is that women and girls naturally require specific nutritional requirements because of their biological needs. Young girls during their puberty stage, young mothers during pregnancy and lactation stage will necessarily require specific food that enable them to be stronger and healthier women. This in turn needs to be recognized as a basic requirement for national well-being and economic growth.

Recommendations for Long-Term Change

As per the observations made in the survey, merely providing food grains through the Public Distribution System or organised livelihood opportunities for rural women do not sufficiently empower women in the context of access to food. Deeper discriminatory practices against women that are social, religious and cultural in nature, need to be simultaneously addressed. If 'right to food' is an intrinsic right to human dignity, there has to be more inclusive strategies which ensure the dignity and worth of woman. Governments and institutions will have to work on understanding the deep-rooted connections with women and food. Such approaches to food security are referred to as gender-transformative approaches in the realm of food security.

1. One such deep-rooted practice that calls for attention is the aspect of gender equality in food security. That women need access to food in equal measure as other family members needs to be squarely addressed through strategic gender interests. Breaching the barriers of discrimination is a hard task. Social institutions such as religion and family can be long term drivers of change to bring about food security in the family.
2. Working towards breaking the gender biases of work and the onus of 'feeding the family' purely as the woman's prerogative is a step towards creating an 'enabling environment' for the wellbeing of women. The creation of an 'enabling environment' has been emphasized in India's 'Policy for Women's Empowerment, 2001'. It states that the gender disparity manifests itself in various forms, the most obvious being the trend of continuously declining female ratio in the population in the last few decades.
3. Social stereotyping and violence at the domestic and societal levels are some of the other manifestations. Discrimination against girl children, adolescent girls and women persists in parts of the country. The institutions of family and faith can play a major role in creating fundamental reforms in beliefs systems in the family thereby mitigating such discriminatory practices.
4. Women in most developing societies face challenges in three critical stages viz, infancy, childhood, adolescent and reproductive phase. Practitioners must pay focused attention in meeting the nutritional needs of women in all stages of her life cycle. These needs should be marked as priority before embarking on empowering women in other aspects of empowerment.
5. Household discrimination in nutritional matters for adolescent girls, pregnant and lactating women must be mitigated though special efforts in changing attitudes and

mind-sets of men and even women. The ideological and cultural belief that the woman eats last or the leftovers after the man and sons of the house is a belief that cannot be erased easily. The belief that the girl child will one day leave the home to another and that she need not be educated or given priority leaves the woman less healthy perpetuating ill-health and a diseased society.

6. Infrastructural needs such as drinking water and sufficient sanitation also requires special attention. Sewage disposal, toilet facilities and sanitation within accessible reach of the households especially in rural and urban slums need attention.

In conclusion for solutions to work, values and meanings attached to roles and identities of women and men, and the likely challenges in enabling and legitimizing women's roles and work need recognition. Women (and men) are not unified, homogenous categories; gender relations are embedded within a complex web of social relations. In the case of India, gender relations intersect not only with wider relations of caste, ethnicity, and class but equally with age and stage in the life cycle, to shape the vulnerabilities confronted by and opportunities available to differently positioned women and men (Rao et al 2017).

Alongside ensuring adequate, nutritious food as a right, one is also challenging, renegotiating, and transforming previously unequal gender relationships. Gender justice in relation to food, femininity and family wellbeing, then, is about wider notions of social transformation based on principles of equality and well-being that stem from cultural and religious identities. Most importantly institutions of family and faith can be the long-term drivers of social change.

Impious Violence in the Name of Jihad: An Unprecedented Experience of Muslims

Yusuf Amin

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When Father Kuruvilla said, “Indifference to God need not be juxtaposed to violence in His name” or something to that effect, as the conversation occurred six months back in July,18 in the Papal Seminary in Pune, it appeared it appeared he was referring to West's secularism and the allegedly violent religiosity of the Muslim Ummah. At that moment , I knew I had a valuable truth to communicate. As a Muslim and insider, I can vouch that the quintessential Muslim, who up to now is the most numerous too, ascribes his/her woes to ‘Actions’. “Our actions have become bad” (*Hamare ámaal kharab ho gae hain*) is the refrain when two Muslims ruminate over their problems. They unreservedly hold their own lack of piety to be the real reason for their problems. The ‘Other’, the ‘Enemies of Islam’ come a distant second. The greater the link with orthodoxy and tradition (in juxta-

position to the contemporary/the modern/the western) the greater is this distance, and vice versa too.

When it comes to ‘Enemies of Islam’, I must admit, there is a misjudgment-begetting laziness of thought in distinguishing between true enemies and those who are merely indifferent or those who *could* be non-violently disappreciating simply by the force of the implicit negative pole of their positive beliefs. This indiscrimination has the biggest harm of making one averse to those not deserving it and in not recognizing and exploring potential areas of true though partial friendships. But this laziness of vision never translates to hostile *action*. The quintessential Muslim, both the commoner and social leader, will never condone hostile acts against those not actively anti-Muslim. Further, the quintessential Muslim would also never condone immoral acts (e.g. burning, mutilation, harming of women, children, elderly, religious figures, etc.) even against actual enemies. It may be surprising that an apparently peripheral issue, namely, the canonical ‘Laws of War’ is a very vivid and central part of the consciousness of both an ordinary or religiously-learned person. Likely resting as much on the moral outlook shaped by the Qura’nic injunction: as on a surprising inclusion of this peripheral issue of ‘Laws of War’ in the basic catechism commonly repeated in religious lectures, it usually does not allow the commission of such barbaric and shameful acts.

The Islamic teachings to take up arms for *what can be truly shown to be* a ‘War for the sake of God’ or *Jihad /Qital fi sabil Allah*, has always spiritually enthused the Muslim Ummah. To my knowledge, the Muslim judgment of the impiety of ISIL’s violence is a first in their history to doubt and condemn a battle in the name of Islam as impious and infernal. There is consensus in Muslim mind (this author included) about

Israel and (Political) America being the architect and puppeteer behind ISIL. But what the author points out - while not being so sure of the concurrence of substantial numbers of his co-religionists - is that the fact of thousands of Muslim youth joining ISIL makes us responsible for recognizing the rot and striving to stamp it out.

However, it is for the non-Muslim sector of humanity to also recognize and confront the 300-year-old colonialist marauding in Muslim lands, epical both in intensity and wickedness, and also to note that the great majority of Muslim resistance being in the face of most inhuman colonialism, deserves acceptance and even support. Yet, given the enormity of the evil of ISIL Muslims and all religious persons have not only to disavow and confront them but to do much brain-storming to discover the reasons for this unprecedented development in the history of Muslims and also to work out the ways to eradicate the very bases of this monstrosity. In these other religious communities too should help the Muslims, as Muslims should help them in their unprecedented problems such as child abuse in the Christian Church and feralization of Hindu youth. Religions are not only rivals but allies as well. Particularly in these last murky times (*Qurb e Qayamat*/Proximity to Doomsday) or *Kaliyuga* when Eternity is most hid the ally-aspect of religions needs to be accentuated. Instead of gloating over each other's unprecedented and challenging failures, they must put such failures in perspectivae before the genral humanity being instigated by secularism in the name of challenging these failures to rebel against religion as such, and help each other in tackling these failures to keep greatest possible number of men and women in access to eternal felicity and its worldly concomitants. Conversion should not be attempted by subversion of other religions but as an exercise in their fulfillment. This would mitigate the strain placed on the inter-religious fraternity by this greatest of divider too.

The Formation of G.P.S Priests!

Naveen Rebello SVD

Biblicum, Rome

Pope Francis, informally addressing the Union of Superior Generals on 29 November 2013, noted that the religious formation today “calls for a different attitude. For example, problems are not solved simply by forbidding doing this or that. Dialogue, as well as confrontation, are needed... Dialogue must be serious, without fear, sincere.... Formation is a work of art, not a police action. We must form their hearts. Otherwise we are creating little monsters. And then these little monsters mold the People of God. This really gives me goose bumps.”¹

True to the above words of Pope Francis, the formation of the seminarians in the Catholic Seminaries today is both a privileged and a demanding task. The formation programme is envisioned to help them become integrated persons for the priestly ministry in the Church. It is envisaged to assist the overall growth of the seminarians with an emphasis on spiritual, human (physical and emotional), intellectual, pastoral and missionary dimensions, so that they go through proper discernment and personal interiorization. The enriching

formation programme also fosters a sense of belongingness, freedom with responsibility, transparency and accountability, punctuality and affective maturity, openness and promptness, morals and faith-based convictions, and empowers them to face the global and local challenges of our day. However, even after such a long period of holistic formation the desired results in the pastoral field or in the missionary front beyond the protective walls of the seminary seem to be discouraging and dissatisfactory.

In my recent conversation with a group of laity concerning the expectations that they have from the present and would-be-clergy, three formative aspects stood out very strongly. They expect a Catholic priest or a Seminarian to be:

1. A God-centred person (G)
2. A People-friendly person (P)
3. A Service-minded person (S)

1. Priest as a God-Centred Person

Today, our faithful seek a priest who is a man of God, living and witnessing God's tenderness and inspires a life of holiness. A God-centered priest through his witnessing life and sanctifying ministry strives to move towards a God-centred existence. The focus of his priestly ministry is 'God' and not 'self'. He is aware that his vocation as a priest is an unconditional gift and not his merit or achievement. In administering and celebrating the sacraments, he shows profound 'devotion' and not merely an external 'performance' of some ostentatious rituals coupled with superficial piety. The faithful entrusted to his care see him praying and being available for their spiritual needs 24X7. They feel the warmth

of a fatherly figure and the tenderness of a good shepherd in him. To the faithful, his spiritual fatherhood models the love of God and others in service. They fear him if he turns out to be a ‘religious nut’, whose insistence on religious duties and obligations demonstrates rigidity and scrupulosity.

The journey to be a God-centred priest begins already in the formation house. In addition to his academic, human and pastoral formation, a seminarian takes his spiritual formation seriously and responsibly. No wonder, “the heart of spiritual formation is personal union with Christ, which is born of, and nourished in, a particular way by prolonged and silent prayer. By prayer, listening to the Word, devout participation in the sacraments, in the liturgy and in community life, the seminarian fortifies his personal union with God after the example of Christ, who had, as his programme of life to do the will of His Father (cf. Jn 4:34).” (*The Gift of the Priestly Vocation* 102). The self-transforming prayer and reflective silence for personal interiorization are the greatest values that he can cultivate in order to discover the spiritual gifts that he is being blessed with, for the priestly life. Regular practice of *Lectio Divina*, daily participation in the Eucharist, praying the Liturgy of the hours, meaningful celebration of the sacrament of Penance, seeking timely spiritual direction are some of the privileged means through which he can attain the goal of his spiritual life, that is to establish a deep union with God. In short, formation for God-centred existence is the foundational dimension in the shaping of the spirituality of a would-be priest.

2. Priest as a People-Friendly Person

The God-centred existence or God-closeness of a priest is clearly manifested in his closeness to the people. Evidently,

the people seek a priest, who is truly human and genuinely compassionate, who has the ability to listen and understand them. What they appreciate the most is their pastor's ability to accompany them, not only in their faith formation but also in their ordinary lives, marked by joys and sorrows, ups and downs, happiness and sorrows. As Pope Francis would say that the true vocation and mission of a priest is to be and to become a "shepherd with the smell of the sheep". Following this analogy, a priest becomes enriched not only by his personal experiences and encounters with the people but also by the experiences of his flock which he brings into the breaking of the Word and its sharing in his homily that truly becomes "the touchstone for judging a pastor's closeness and ability to communicate to his people" (*GPV* 177).

This brings to the fore the human and pastoral formation of the seminarians in our context today. The priestly formation is always permeated by a pastoral spirit. Rightly said, to be pastoral is to be human first, so that we exclude none and include everyone. In this regard, the pastoral formation intends to prepare the seminarians for the *pastoral accompaniment* of children, young people, sick, elderly, disabled, and those who live in situations of isolation and poverty. Accompanied by human formation, it helps them become humanly balanced, serene and stable, valuing inter-personal relationships, so that they become priests with friendly traits, who are authentic, loyal, interiorly free, affectively stable, capable of weaving together peaceful inter-personal relationships and living the evangelical counsels or the promises without rigidity, hypocrisy or loopholes. The desired result is to become experts in the "art of pastoral discernment", that is, the ability to listen deeply to the real situations of the people (*GPV* 120). Further,

the courses on homiletics help them integrate the real-life issues of people with insights from the Word of God than merely communicate some abstract theological ideas that affect neither the preacher nor his faithful. In short, a truly human priest visibly manifests the true and unconditional love of God to people both in words and deeds.

3. Priest as a Service-Minded Person

A priest manifests his God-centredness and Pastoral-closeness through his service. His priestly ministry is based on the conviction that ‘others’ come before the ‘self’. The selfless service of a priest demonstrates that the divine is concretely experienced in the service of the other (Mt 25: 34-40). To a service-minded priest, having ‘no time’ is never an excuse, for he always takes time out of his busy schedule to address the issues that affect his faithful. Today, in many quarters of the church, the faithful complain about their priest regarding his unavailability and the misuse of power and pastoral resources, arrogance and self-righteous attitude, arbitrary and autocratic behaviour based on personal whims and fancies. Regular meetings, cells, associations, and celebrations keep the priest ‘busy’, thus making him more of a ‘functionary’ and his activity more of work devoid of genuine love.

To become a service-minded priest, the formation helps a seminarian to identify what is essential and non-essential. Work makes one tired, but service keeps one joyful, for it is done in the name of the Lord. The weekend-ministries (both social and pastoral), if taken seriously, become a real source of joy, that not only expose the seminarian to the concrete human realities around him but also immerse him to face more challenges boldly. And as a seminarian, if he finds himself happiest when being of service to others, he can be

certain that his future ministry as a priest would be a joyful and sacrificial one in the likeness of Jesus, who “came not to be served but to serve” (Mk 10:45). Therefore, the formation programme assists a seminarian to become a priest who puts the interests of the community before his, more of service-minded, less of power-hungry, more of available and less of busy and more of joyful in ministry and less of depressed, burdened and unhappy.

To conclude, let us wish that the priestly formation in India may truly become an authentic process of shaping God-centred, people-friendly, and service-minded priests (G.P.S), whose holiness of spiritual life, the accompaniment of pastoral life and the humility and simplicity of personal life bring people closer to God.

Notes

1. Antonio Spadaro, “Wake up the World: Conversation with Pope Francis about the Religious Life”, *La Civiltà Cattolica* I (2014), pp. 8-9.

Searching for Meaning in Dying

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The theme I have chosen to explore as my mode of discourse over the topic of life and death is the one on the philosophy of death. I have come to realise that death is sometimes looked at as a negative outcome in one's journey of life. It is a concept that paves into too many ambiguities and is perceived differently in unfathomable numbers of belief systems all across the world. There have been many prevailing accounts on the conception of death throughout the course of history, and to summarise a well-versed understanding on how it is conceptualised and integrated into cultures, I felt it was necessary to build my own perspective upon the same. To explore what it means to me, I felt I needed to conduct my research on those who illuminated the idea of death through the course of their work and lives. In my opinion, there wouldn't have been a more accurate account of the representation of death, than those coming from two philosophers whose work entailed pieces that added to the process of understanding what it is.

I have to be honest in saying that their works did not prove any conclusive statements, nor did they entertain any pre-conceived notions that may find themselves surrounding the

talk of death. I did not find anything that spoke of a definite afterlife, or even anything about semi-conscious post-natal states. I did, however, learn a lot about how to formulate my worldview and use what I know today to serve as a means to understand what to expect of what I don't know. Researching on these philosophers helped me in rationalising the realities of life, identifying with who I am as a person and what death means to me. I don't look for meaning where there isn't any to find, although I can confidently say that death does play a very important role in how one leads one's life. I realised there are some ground-rules to remember when attempting to conceptualise something as vague as death. I hope this essay bifurcates from the ambiguities of life, paying emphasis on how to distinguish a rational understanding of the same.

The main objective of my research is to find meaning to the idea of death. I feel death is an unexplored means of human action, it can be viewed as an essential characteristic to add meaning into one's life. I believe death makes way for life, and hence cannot be deemed negative. In order to assess its true nature, I chose to include the works of two notable philosophers who have devoted their lives in developing an authentic account of this concept. I feel as if death when left open to debate can stimulate ambiguous representations that may vary in their accuracy. When I say that, I imply it in terms of their capability in assimilating and graphing the sophistications that lie in such an unexplored aspect. I have used all of their most established works and tried to correlate them into a conclusion I have come to happenstance by myself. The aim of the essay is to derive a more conclusive account of life, something that offers the reader with a little more specification on the dos and don'ts of life and existence, and how to make the most of one's predicament.

Paul Ricoeur, revered for his work in the field of continental philosophy talks in his works about death, immortality, life, mortality and natality. In engaging perceptions on what it means to live, and arguments about how death can only be through life - ergo only be defined through life, he takes us through his beliefs on what it means to lead a nourishing life. In his final work, *Living up to Death*, explains how the act of death is an act of life since death is the elimination of life thereby disengaging from the idea of an afterlife. He too draws inspiration from the works of other scholars such as Sigmund Freud, and adds his insight on the idealism of the works of mourning and detachment, two subsidiaries that consequence the act of death. Here, detachment is described as letting go of the attachment to/off any object, the loss of which is equivalent to the loss of self. This brackets off imaginary projection of an afterlife or any form of personal resurrection. Through my essay, I aim to supplement a breakdown of all the writings and claims made on this ideology.

Martin Heidegger, another continental philosopher born in Nazi Germany offers an alternative approach to the idealisms surrounding life, death and the things that lie in between. His evaluation of death is drawn primarily from his work *Being and Time*, in which he discusses the relevance of self-identity and the significance of time in its development. He views death as a taboo for a topic, refrained from being open to discussion by the likes of those he deems to be cowards i.e., people incapable of understanding death in its most natural sense. He broadly explains how the body is learning death from the moment it is formed, using analogies such as the ripening of a fruit. The subjectivity of death lies in the intricacies of the being, and Heidegger argues that a more logical approach to death would be embracing it for its nature and using it to focus on one's own existence. Heidegger, I find,

has a rather uplifting approach towards death as it is only in relation to death that one truly becomes aware of one's freedom.

Ricoeur claims that the idea following a narrative deciphers the crux of one's arrival to one's own identity. We are in the constant ebb and flow of a story that we continue to create till we die, and we are all its characters and themes. Even if the story isn't our own, to derive something significant from the story that superimposes meaning onto our own lives, is the aim of such narrative. In effect, narrative identity helps one encounter answers to questions that appraise and validate life; "who am I? where am I going?"

The narrative sets us in the path of assertion of the self. Whether the self is a physical, turgid, conscious entity or whether the self is a metaphysical, passive, subconscious one is solely reliant on the narrative we see it through. It then has the capability of being both abstract or limited. His argument proceeds through several different layers of thought. The first acknowledgment of the self is through the language used in its narrative, identifying the facilitator of it as an agent of life passing through the semantics of action. Then after is asserting the self through one's narrative identity, and this is followed by the ethical ramifications that lie within what makes the self. It means to ask and acknowledge what is "I" and when is "I", which is lived through conviction rather than scientific certainty.

If Martin Heidegger's work *Being and Time* has taught us anything, it is the fact that death has been a tabooed or under-spoken means of discourse over time due to its inexplicable and nonfigurative nature. His use of language through this work is a slave to its time, making it a product of an innovative means of discussion. What I have chosen to consider

for my research is a segment of this work which illuminates Heidegger's take on death as an unexplored characteristic of existence. To understand one's existence as a whole, one must differentiate the authentic self from the inauthentic self. One's life shifts its focus through the narrative chosen by oneself. To justify its use, one must choose to process thought in its most authentic form.

Heidegger, in his own writings has managed to address issues surrounding immortality, life after death and the nature of death during one's own existence. He includes death as a prerequisite to life, just as is, one could argue, the case with war and peace. He implies man is a whole entity called Existence or Dasein. Existence, through his death, comes aware of the finite nature of his being, ultimately realizing why he has been termed existence. Existentialism is the outcome of the acceptance of death as a characteristic of life. As, it is only through one's own existence, that one can provide life with meaning and definition. This argument diverges into subsidiary philosophies that may argue against any actualized, uniform and unanimous definitions. This is because I can only claim to know what I have come to know through my own time and place on this planet. Only through my own existence and being can I cast a notion or definition of and on something. Thus, it is only one's existence that is then actualized, uniform and unanimous.

“Expression is existence”. To conceptualize hermeneutics into Paul Ricoeur's understanding of it, one must accept the notion that his work is contemporary and that he deems it to transcend the barricades of culture and time. He regards hermeneutics to be a moderm of self-actualization and self-understanding. He claims both explicitly and implicitly that in order to develop this understanding of the

self, one must understand what surrounds this self. Thus, self-comprehension is derived from comprehending others. One's existence is arranged in a chronological, linear setting. We compartmentalize the events of our lives with the help of such a setting to formulate a more organized flow of thought. There is a beginning, an ongoing and an ending. All of what we know fits through these quantifications, and what is unknown to us is what lies beyond them. Through the means of others who have existed before us, ergo, expressed before us – we generate meaning to life. Through the lives and expressions of what those before us have left behind, we build notions and meanings that support our understanding of our own existence.

With regards to death, it isn't something one can express. But as we all come to know in different, unique ways of our own, death can be left behind through experiences of those who came before us. One of the most relevant themes that can be found in Ricoeur's writings is that of philosophical anthropology. He devised an idea around what he considered to be a capable human being. Through his work, he strives to generate a comprehensive account of the vulnerabilities, inhibitions, talents and capabilities that humans display through the course of their lives. He categorizes these activities as relevant to sustaining their coexistence as a species and terms them as responsible human action. Although he tries to create an understanding to the notion of what becomes the self, he claims that this identity is reserved and not transparent to its proprietor. The self can only be made apparent through the relationship the proprietor has shared with what surrounds them, their relationship with the world and its cohabitants.

To come to these conclusions, Ricoeur often shifted the themes in his discourse in order to categorize his intellectual

settings to adjust to new developments. Often, questioning and challenging his own work, he practiced reflexive thought to broaden the spectrum of questions asked about the field of his study. Most of his initial publications were either the product of war, or came about to be during them. From what he had learnt in his academic years, he came to understand how the “I” or self, comes aware, creates meaning, thinks, acts and ultimately exits through reflexive consciousness.

Although Dasein or The Self cannot experience its own death as actual, what it can do is always know its inevitability, and therefore be before it. That is, to embrace the idea of death before it limits physical existence to achieve metaphysical freedom. Dasein cannot confirm death, only avail its possibility since after death, there is no Dasein. Death then, through Dasein, can be defined as “possibility of the impossibility of any existence at all”. Through the omnipresence of death around Dasein, one must acknowledge death as a means of non-relationality, that is to cut all ties from everything. This stems from the radicle implication that one’s death is one’s own. It is through this acknowledgment of one’s non-existence that one can engage in the ability of being-able-to-be to not-being at all. Awareness of one’s own death as an omnipresent possibility discloses one’s most honest predicament. It is here when one can deliberate the most authentic version of the self. Dasein too, then is a finite being.

This awareness towards one’s death creates a realization of a concept coined as being-toward-death. It is to live through recognizing death. Anxiety here is not necessarily considered as a negative characteristic to the make of the being, but rather a provider of the knowledge needed to carry out decisions made around one’s existence. This gives rise to the authentic and the inauthentic birth of the self. When

the self is anxious, it sees the world as intangible. Here, the possibilities of the world moving forward without the self are brought to light along with the ontological sense of not-being or un-being and the acceptance of 'nothing' as an outcome. This is the authentic self.

The inauthentic self, deals with evasion of such concepts. Here the self considers it to be of higher significance by abstaining death from adding meaning into its existence. This does not mean that one would disregard the possibility of one's own death, rather, it is to operate without computing the certainty of death through one's actions. To validate this, one's own death cannot ever be witnessed by them. Therefore, it isn't incorrect to say I will never experience my own death. In my metaphysical understanding of the concept, I can live forever through my own perspective.

Inauthenticity of the self can also come through fear. Fear of the notion of death can generate fake responses, as it is to live as if one is experiencing death when in reality, one isn't. This is contrasting to anxiety, which is to perceive a world without oneself. Let me use an example to explain this difference more appropriately. When I go to a bar in the attempt to try a new kind of cocktail, I can either anticipate the flavor of my drink or I can expect the flavor of my drink. What happens here is, when I expect the flavor of my drink, I am waiting for an actual sequence of events to occur. I have already asserted my cocktail with a quality. However, if I anticipate its taste, it is making me aware of the possibility of how it may taste. So, in a cognitive sense, I go out to meet that possibility - thus owning that experience. Expecting death is waiting for a death to happen, anticipating one's death is owning it.

The Dasein is a finite being. If we were infinite, immortal

beings, learning would happen directly. We wouldn't have to pour hours of time pondering away at the complexities of our own existence, but rather learn them as they are. Since we are finite beings, our learning happens indirectly. We learn through metaphors or connotations or abstractions or vagueness. Our learning is interpretational, and meaning to things change with the ebb and flow of time. We do not have a definitive understanding of anything, let alone death. What we can do is learn through the example of others. In a nihilistic point of view, we can argue that death is the outcome to all existence, it is what completes life's journey and gives it meaning. Life can be considered a fable wherein the way you die defines the purpose of your being, it can be looked at as the moral of one's story. To fully assess what it means to have died a significant death, one must live a significant life. The judge of this significance is based solely on what is derived off the experiences one has endured. The indirect learning here can either satisfy one's existence or contradict it. But in the case of life, there are almost never any binaries. There is never a definitive good or a definitive bad. It's not black, nor white, but a colossal amount of grey. Death to me has always been an area that stirs much debate. I have read plenty on its cause and effects, its nature, its nurture. Something as limiting as death can be enough for one to fully explore the potential that lies within one's existence, however, we are so caught up in trying to justify our deaths that we forget living.

“Pain is temporary” was one of the last things that were said to me before the passing of an individual I held very dearly. There is so little and yet so much in that said phrase, maybe the timing of which makes it all the more profound. It is a statement that holds true throughout age and tide. Pain is another aspect of life, along with death, love and

happiness. Pain is growth, and one can only become more through pain. Death can cause pain, which can cause growth. Pain is temporary, as is life. The finite nature of being and time was exposed through a phrase, that at the time of it being said, could have meant nothing. Maybe because I have come to address this loss, and because this was said to me very close to the departure of this individual, I have read more into it. But maybe that is the point of one's narrative or Dasein. Maybe, the means through which one can achieve immortality is through insignificant phrases like this said at significant times. Or maybe it could be through creation and procreation. We have come to understand how ideologies may live on forever, but I feel ideologies then are what you may intend to make of them. The subjective nature of information processing dwindles the possibility of any particular criteria from staying relevant.

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of the Bombay Province of the Society of Jesus for their help and encouragement by supplying us with the relevant materials.

The Title, *Melodies from the Flute*

Indeed, this book is a tribute to Noel Sheth from his colleagues and friends. We affirm that Noel has tirelessly worked for inter-religious dialogue, has attempted dialogue between science and religion and has assiduously sought for wisdom deeply rooted in our Indian traditions and the Christian heritage!

(Bibliography Details: Pandikattu, Kuruvila and Thomas Kari-mundackal (eds) *Melodies from the Flute: Dialogue Among Religions and Cultures : Memorial Volume for Indian Christian Philosopher Rev Noel Sheth SJ.* , New Delhi: Christian World Imprints, 2018 ISBN: 978-93-5148-325-0 (HB) pp. 332+xvii.)

Melodies from the Flute: A Tribute to Prof Noel Sheth SJ

Kuruvilla Pandikattu SJ

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A man of ahimsa, compassion and dialogue! That was, indeed, Prof. Noel Kantilal Sheth SJ. Calm and sober in his attitude, he reached out to others respectfully and reverentially. His meticulous and methodological nature and analytic-synthetic mind made him a humble servant, erudite scholar, efficient teacher and responsible administrator. He had a good eye for details and would plan his personal, professional, academic life extremely meticulously. He reached out to other traditions, religions and cultures with a warm heart and open arms, so that our world may be a better and more peaceful place. He mastered Sanskrit so well that he could authoritatively read and interpret the Indian religious texts. This made him reach out to the Hindu scholars. He learnt also Pali which made him reach out to the Buddhist scholars and devotees. His scholarship enabled him to build bridges between Hinduism, Buddhism and Christianity, so that we could understand and appreciate each other (including our genuine differences and creative diversities) better. Prof. Noel Sheth SJ passed away on July 8, 2017, sadly and unexpectedly at Bagota Columbia (local date: July 7).

To commemorate meaningfully his 75th birthday (October 31, 2018), some of us, his friends, well-wishers and colleagues, decided to bring out this memorial volume. In the Call for Papers send out to the writers, the following mission and vision of the life of Prof Sheth were recalled.

- Unwaveringly compassionate
- Reaching out to the other
- Dialoguing differently
- Compassionate and reverential dialogue
- Compassion (karuna), dialogue and service
- Good teacher; gentleman; calm and sober
- Respect and reverence for all
- Meticulous, analytic-synthesis
- Passionately compassionate

The general thrust was to convey the message and mission of Noel Sheth, accordingly we also proposed tentatively the following titles of the articles that could be written:

- “Divinity of Krishna:” An Appraisal
- Hindu-Christian engagement
- Muslim-Christian dialogue
- Identity-Conflict-Development
- Buddhist Concern and Compassion to Other Religions
- Subaltern perspectives on Living Together
- Christian Appreciation of the Other
- Befriending the Other
- Indian Genius for Religious Harmony
- Alliance of Civilizations
- An Indian Ending
- Praxis as Testing Ground for Theory
- Altruism: Christian and Beyond
- Science-Religion Dialogue
- The Value of Comparative Philosophy and Theology
- The Flute of Krishna
- “Religious and Cultural Resources for Peace”

General Overview of the Book

This book is about encountering other traditions, building friendly bridges with them, affirming others compassionately, enabling them and appreciating their diversity and difference, through dialogue, interaction and cooperation. The first article by Rudy Heredia, a close friend of Noel Sheth, sets the general tone when he reflects on triple dialogue as learning together with the other. The next section of articles delves on the Christian heritage and base that urges to

affirm the other. Dr. Boris Repschinski SJ, University of Innsbruck, Austria, elaborates on welcoming and affirming hospitality, where he deals with the creative tension between Jesus as guest and God as host. The next article by Dr. Thomas Karimundackal bases himself on the Biblical wisdom tradition and looks for metaphors of wisdom in the Indian traditions, especially in the Upanishadic and Vaishnavite traditions. The next article by Rekha M. Chennattu, Superior General, Religious of the Assumption, delves into the need to build bridges, drawing from the New Testament. The following section explores the Indian roots of both Prof. Noel Sheth and the readers. The first article by Prof. Selva Rathinam, President, Jnana-Deepa Vidyapeeth, looks at the wisdom of the Book of Qoheleth and compares it with the Indian thought. Taking a more concrete step, the Israeli scholar, Ithamar Theodor, exposes the centrality of Gītā and its profound relationship to non-Hindu religions. In the next article, Prof Nishant Irudayadason, Papal Seminary, Pune, bases himself on the ethical subjectivity of Levinas and shows that the Tamil Vaishnavite tradition, particularly Andal has shown us that the erotic love can also be a way towards the divine. The succeeding article by Dolichan Kollareth, De Nobili College, Pune, studies the psychoanalysis of Girindrasekhar Bose as a model for East-West dialogue.

The final article in this section by Prof. Victor Ferrao, Dean, Rachol Seminary, reflects on translation between self and the other as a prelude to dialogue, especially in the Goan context, which may be applied to the larger Indian scenario. The next section on “The Religious Vision,” talks of the diversity of religious traditions that is characteristic of India. Professor James Ponniah, University of Madras, revisits comparative approaches in the study of religion for contemporary times, providing new insights on the need for a creative study of comparative religions. While J. Charles Davis, Albert Ludwigs University of Freiburg, Germany, explores human dignity in Islam as a bridging space for dialogue, M.D. Joseph, Research Fellow, Jnana-Deepa Vidyapeeth, Pune studies the emancipatory dimension of subaltern religions. Vadappuram M. Jose, Jnana-Deepa Vidyapeeth, pleads for religious harmony and sees in Prof. Noel Sheth that Indian genius, who is the need of the hour.

The next set of articles reflects Noel Sheth’s attempts at dialogu-

ing between science and religion. He himself has many articles in this area. While two scientists Donald Frohlich, University of St. Thomas, Houston and Felipe Andrés Piedra, Baylor College of Medicine, Houston, reflects on biology and philosophy to reach a unity, Prof. Stephen Jayard, Jnana-Deepa Vidyapeeth, focusses on Nanotechnology and Prof. Kamladevi Kunkolienker, P.E.S.' College of Arts and Science, Farmagudi-Ponda-Goa sees science-religion dialogue as a necessary component in our pursuit for happiness.

The final section explores our life as essentially dialogical. Kuvilla Pandikattu studies the philosophical basis for dialogue. Rev Sr Mudita Menona Sodder, Sophia College, Mumbai, pleads for inter-faith dialogue for ecological justice and peace on earth.

Rt Rev Thomas Menampampil Emeritus Bishop of Guwahati affirms the need for The Dialogue of Civilizations, following the model of Matteo Ricci, the great Italian Jesuit of 16th century with his Chinese connection. The next article by Dr. Keith D'Souza, St. Xavier's College, Mumbai, proposes the requirements or criteria for religion as a pathway for peace. The concluding article by Prof. Subhah Anand, a close friend and colleague of Prof. Sheth at Pune, looks at humans as pilgrims going beyond every code, cult, community and creed in our journey to the Divine!

We have conveniently divided the 21 articles into five sections, which are named after some of the deepest aspirations and hopes of Prof. Sheth. We hope that his vision and mission will be carried on by his colleagues, companions and friends. May this book contribute to a better harmony among our different religious traditions! May it help us to learn deeply from others' religious traditions and grow in wisdom. May this book be an inspiration to reach out to everyone and everything with compassion, wisdom and love!

Since this book values diversity, we have not uniformalised the technical details. While trying to be accurate and rigorous in its content, we have left the authors the freedom to follow their own methodology of research. We are really grateful to the staff and community of both Papal Seminary and JnanaDeepa Vidyapeeth, Pune, for encouraging this venture. We also thank the Provincial and Socius

(Contd on p. 36)